

Di(*ortho*-hydroxybenzylidene)acetone as a new acid-base indicator and a chromogenic receptor for anions and guanidine

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Abstract : The development of a new simple acid-base indicator di(*o*-hydroxybenzylidene)acetone (1) is reported as a possible alternative to phenolphthalein and its performance has been compared with those of *o*-hydroxybenzylideneacetone (2) and *p*-hydroxybenzylideneacetone (3), two synthetic compounds, and curcumin (4), a natural product occurring in turmeric. Among the four compounds, 1 is found to be the best. It may also be used in the titration of guanidine in non-aqueous solvents (e.g. in dry alcohol). It is also shown to be a chemosensor for anions.

Keywords : Acid base indicator, di(*o*-hydroxybenzylidene)acetone, guanidine, receptor for anions and guanidine.

Introduction

Lewis¹ in 1923 reconciled the proton and solvent system theories to define acids and bases in terms of neutralisation and titration with indicators and he first suggested² electronic explanation for acid base phenomena which Sidgwick³ later called acceptor molecules. Thus most acid base indicators are generally colored substances (though phenolphthalein is a colorless solid) and in solution, they change color according to acidity or alkalinity. The rapid change of pH near the stoichiometric point of an acid base titration is the basis of indicator detection and an acid base indicator is an organic tautomeric molecule that has different colors in acid (HIn) and conjugate base (In-forms). The end point of a reaction may be detected by many methods. Titrations often use visual indicators (the reaction mixture changes color). In simple acid base titrations a pH indicator may be used, such as phenolphthalein, which becomes pink when a certain pH (about 8.2) is reached or exceeded. Similarly methyl orange, is red in acids and yellow in alkali solutions. The color change using litmus happens over an unusually wide range and thus it is not useful for titration but it is useful for detecting acids and alkalis because it changes color around pH 7 unlike methyl orange or phenolphthalein where color change happens in pH range 3.1–4.4 or 8.3–10.0 respectively.

We have shown here that di(*o*-hydroxybenzylidene)-

acetone (1), *o*-hydroxybenzylideneacetone (2) and *p*-hydroxybenzylideneacetone (3) [and they are also compared with curcumin (4), isolated from natural turmeric known for hundreds of years in food preparation] (Fig. 1) can be used as indicators in acid base titrations like phenolphthalein and indicator 1 is the best choice compared to 2 and 3 for its sensitivity and also due to the sharp contrast in the change of color in the end point from yellow (in acid) to red (in alkali).

Fig. 1. Organic indicators (1, 2, 3 and 4) for acid-base system.

Results and discussion

The synthesis of the compounds 1, 2 and 3 (Scheme 1) is simple and known nearly one hundred years ago. In this paper, it is shown that they are very efficient and useful as indicators for acid-base titrations and the same titrations are also done with natural curcumin (4) and the results are compared with the common versatile phenol-

phthalein for their efficacy as acid-base indicators^{4,5}. The end point using **1** as indicator is sharp and show a clean contrast from yellow to red and the color change is distinctly visible by addition of one drop of alkali in excess at the neutralisation point (pH = 8.68, color is red) during titration with acid compared to **2** and **3** (Table 1). The strengths of unknown bases against oxalic acid of known strength are found to be the same when compared with phenolphthalein as an indicator. Curcumin **4** is shown to change from yellow (acid) to orange (alkali) at the end point. However **1** is found to be the best choice amongst these as a possible additional indicator to phenolphthalein.

Table 1. Indicator properties

Indicators	Color in acid	Color in base	Color at the end point ^d
Indicator 1	Yellow	Red	Yellow
Indicator 2	Colorless	Yellow	Colorless
Indicator 3	Colorless	Yellow	Colorless

^dOxalic acid is added dropwise to the solution of sodium hydroxide solution.

The indicators **1** [1,5-bis-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-penta-1,4-dien-3-one], **2** and **3** are thus synthesized by the simple one step condensation reaction of salicylaldehyde or *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde with acetone in alkali as shown above (Scheme 1). It is highly soluble in ethanol, acetonitrile, DMSO and methanol etc.

Scheme 1. Synthesis of indicators **1**, **2** and **3**.

It is partly soluble in water and completely soluble in water-ethanol mixture (1 : 1). Solubility also is thus as good as phenolphthalein. It is safe, stable, and nonhygroscopic. The product from the direct reaction flask after neutralization becomes pure after a couple of washings with distilled water followed by drying in air.

Colors of indicator 1 in dilute as well as strong acid or alkali :

Indicator **1** is yellow in the solid state and also in the solution. It is interesting to see the colors of indicator **1** in dilute or very strong acid or alkali (Figs. 2–6) and thus it is important to check the possible transformed structural forms in different pH (Fig. 3) and the possible resonance structures are also shown in Fig. 4. By addition of alkali, the acidic phenolic hydroxyl group is ionized to the phenolate ion where the negative charges of both mono-anionic form (**1a**) and di-anionic form (**1b**) (Fig. 3) are delocalized. The resonance structures of the dianion of the indicator **1** are shown in Fig. 4 which are more stabilized and the dianion shows red color (Figs. 6–9). In UV experiments, the λ_{\max} value shifts to visible range (longer wavelength) (Fig. 10) which also supports the statement mentioned before.

In titration of a 0.1 (M) NaOH solution with 0.1 N oxalic acid, a sharp change of color from yellow to red (due to dianion **1b**) is observed without the intermediate orange color (mono-anion **1a**) which is however observed during careful addition of NaHCO₃ (on addition of excess NaHCO₃ or on prolonged keeping with NaHCO₃ the solution turns red).

Fig. 2. Indicator **1** in very strong acid or alkali.

Fig. 3. Structures of mono-ionized (**1a**) and di-ionised (**1b**) forms of indicator **1**.

Fig. 4. Resonance structures of conjugate base (dianion 1b) of indicator 1

Though the color of the indicator 1 in dilute acid or weak acid is yellow, the color in very strong acid (conc. HCl or conc. H₂SO₄) is also red (like that in dilute alkali due to presence of dianion) which may also be due to high resonance stability of the protonated conjugated carbonyl (Fig. 5). The colors of the indicators 1, 3 and 4 in strong alkali, acid and in neutral solutions are shown in Fig. 6.

Fig. 7(b). Fig. 8 shows the colors of the indicator 1 in different pH values. Thus, both phenolphthalein and our indicator have also the advantage in titration of weak acid and a strong base where color change takes place in a higher pH range. In case of our indicator, color change starts at pH 7.68 which lies in more acidic range than phenolphthalein and thus titrations of weak bases (like sodium bicarbonate) against strong acids with our indica-

Fig. 5. Protonated form of indicator 1 in very strong acid.

Fig. 6. Colors of the indicators 1, 3 and 4 (curcumin) : visible change of colors of the indicators 1, 3 and 4

The colors of indicator 1 at specific pH 3.43 and 10.06 are also shown in Fig. 7(a). The transition pH for color change in titration of oxalic acid versus sodium hydroxide is 8.68. The pH range for the display of color change of our indicator 1 is 7.68–9.68 and that for phenolphthalein is 8.3–10.0. The change of color of indicator 1 from yellow to orange on addition of NaHCO₃ is shown in

Fig. 7. (a) Change of color with change of pH of indicator 1. (b) Orange from yellow with NaHCO₃.

Fig. 8. Colors of indicator 1 in different pH

tor should have better advantage over phenolphthalein [the color change of the indicator in such cases corresponds to yellow from orange due to the presence of the partially ionized **1a** (mono-anion)]. The other important advantage is that the deep red color persists even at strong alkaline pH (13–14) for long where phenolphthalein becomes colorless.

The advantage of non-aqueous titrations of strong bases like guanidine and sodium ethoxide (in alcohol) is also noteworthy. The titration shows same color change as in case of NaOH vs oxalic acid titration.

UV results of indicator 1 :

The UV titrations of indicator **1** which is a di-phenolic (acidic) compound (conjugated with the carbonyl group) with strong and weak bases respectively like NaOH and K_2CO_3 in water (using indicator **1** in 1 : 1 ethanol-water solution) have been performed. Non-aqueous UV titrations of guanidine in absolute ethanol with an ethanolic solution of indicator **1** has also been performed. Indicator **1** is titrated with guanidine in other organic solvents (dissolving both **1** and guanidine) like CH_3CN , DMSO, dry CH_3OH and *t*-butanol respectively (free guanidine liberated from guanidine hydrochloride by sodium ethoxide in ethanol followed by drying under reduced pressure and dissolving in the particular solvent). In these organic solvents, the UV spectra show that intensity of absorbance of indicator **1** is continuously decreasing. However, in case of ethanol solvent, the UV titration curves for indicator **1** and guanidine show isosbestic point at 414 nm (Fig. 9) like those in cases of UV titrations using NaOH, KOH and K_2CO_3 , respectively.

Indicator **1** itself exhibits λ_{max} at 373 nm in 1 : 1 ethanol in water and it shows a large λ -shift (red shift) by addition of NaOH, KOH and K_2CO_3 (all in 1 : 1 ethanol in water) [Fig. 9 : (i), (ii) and (iii) respectively]. Non

aqueous titrations⁶⁻⁹ are important specially in case of estimation of organic bases and indicator **1** may be used in such titrations e.g. guanidine. When indicator **1** is titrated with guanidine solution in dry ethanol, the λ_{max} of UV-Vis spectra of the complex shifts towards longer wavelength (470 nm i.e. visible range) (Fig. 9) (iv)(a). The UV-spectra show two peaks : one at around 373 nm and the other at around 470 nm. The similar titrations of guanidine in other organic solvents are also performed with indicator **1** and the titration curves are shown in (iv)(b) (in CH_3CN), (iv)(c) in DMSO, (iv)(d) in dry CH_3OH and (iv)(e) in *t*-butanol respectively.

The appearance of the red color (Fig. 7) due to addition of alkali to the solution of indicator **1** can be better understood by observation of the UV-spectra. According to Khalaf *et al.*¹¹ the band at around 373 nm is due to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition and the band at around 470 nm is due to charge-transfer (CT) transition¹². The similar observation is found with NaOH or K_2CO_3 when they are complexed with indicator **1**. All these titration curves show isosbestic point at around 414 nm including guanidine in dry ethanol (Fig. 9) (i) to (iv)(a) respectively. The UV spectra of indicator **1** with guanidine in other solvents like CH_3CN , DMSO, CH_3OH and *t*-butanol are also shown in Fig. 9 iv(b) to iv(e) respectively.

The titration curve using this new indicator **1** for oxalic acid versus NaOH is also shown in Fig. 10.

UV results for binding of indicator 1 with anions and guanidine :

We have also studied the binding behavior of the indicator **1** as receptor with a series of anions e.g. F^- , Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , $CH_3CO_2^-$, HO^- and CO_3^{2-} . The halide and acetate salts were taken as tetrabutyl ammonium salts. The UV titration curves are shown in Fig. 11 along with their K_a values. The binding curves are shown in Fig. 12.

Fig. 9. UV spectral change of indicator 1 with (i) NaOH, (ii) KOH, (iii) K₂CO₃, (iv)(a) guanidine in EtOH, (iv)(b) in CH₃CN, (iv)(c) in DMSO, (iv)(d) in CH₃OH, (iv)(e) in *t*-butanol.

Fig. 10. Oxalic acid vs NaOH titration curve using indicator 1.

With the F^- and $CH_3CO_2^-$ anions like strong hydroxide and guanidine bases, indicator 1 shows formation of red color from its original yellow color and thus in these cases 1 behaves as a chromogenic receptor. K_a for F^- and Cl^- are similar and higher than that for Br^- , I^- and acetate and this may be due to larger size and less charge density for the latter anions. The K_a for guanidine is similar to that for hydroxide bases. Interestingly, the binding with carbonate is similar to hydroxide or guanidine which may be due to the tighter binding of symmetrical carbonate anion.

The possible binding modes of indicator 1 with repre-

Fig. 11. UV titration curves for indicator 1 with anions tbaf (tetrabutyl ammonium fluoride), tbac (tetrabutyl ammonium chloride), tbab (tetrabutyl ammonium bromide), tbai (tetrabutyl ammonium iodide) and tbaa (tetrabutyl ammonium acetate) respectively.

Fig. 12. Binding curves for anions and guanidine with the receptor 1.

sentative anions are shown in Fig. 13. In case of anions like fluoride, acetate and also guanidine base, the indicator shows color change from yellow to red. The basicity of the anions is responsible for the possible ionization of the indicator 1 to show color change. The other anions however do not show any visible color change but also bind strongly [possible binding modes are shown in Fig. 13].

Fig. 13. Possible binding modes of anions, F^- and guanidine with the receptor

Conclusion :

We have thus developed a long known compound 1 as a new important indicator (not reported earlier as an acid base indicator to our knowledge) which can be successfully used in acid base titration like the long known phenolphthalein. Thus indicator 1 may be useful as a possible alternative to phenolphthalein. It can also be used in guanidine titration in non-aqueous medium (in dry alcohol). Indicator 1 is also proved to be a good receptor for anions.

Experimental

General :

Melting points (m.p.) were recorded on an A.D. and Co. hot-coil stage melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. UV-Vis spectra were recorded on a JASCO V-530 instrument.

Method for preparation of di(*o*-hydroxybenzylidene)acetone (1) :

In a r.b. flask (500 ml) a cold solution of NaOH (125 g in a mixture of 125 ml of water and 125 ml of ethanol) was taken and stirred. Ice was added. When the temperature of the solution was about 25 °C then one half of the previously prepared mixture of *o*-hydroxybenzaldehyde (15.25 g, 13.31 ml, 0.125 mol) and acetone (3.65 g, 4.65 ml, 0.0629 mol) was added. After 15 min, the remaining solution was added and the stirring was continued further for a period of 30 min. Then the solution was neutralised with acetic acid to give a yellow precipitate which was filtered at the pump, washed with water and dried to afford the pure product 1, yield : 80%, m.p. 125-127 °C.

Indicator 1 : 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$, 400 MHz) : δ 10.29 (2H, br s), 7.93 (2H, d, J 16.08 Hz), 7.69 (2H, d, J 6.56 Hz), 7.29 (2H, d, J 16 Hz), 7.23 (2H, d, J 5.1 Hz), 6.92 (2H, d, J 7.64 Hz), 6.86 (4H, t, J 7.62 Hz).

Compound 2 :

It was also prepared by the above method but there

was an isolation problem in this case. We followed the similar procedure for its preparation but after acidification it afforded no solid residue. Therefore it was extracted with $CHCl_3$ and concentrated under reduced pressure to get a semi-solid crude product. Purification was done by column chromatography using 100-200 mesh silica gel and petroleum ether-EtOAc (85 : 15) as eluant to get a yellow colored desired semi-solid compound 2, yield : 70%, m.p. 65-67 °C; 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$; 300 MHz) : δ 7.85 (1H, d, J 16.44 Hz), 7.49 (1H, d, J 6.9 Hz), 6.97-6.85 (3H, m), 6.43 (1H, s), 2.42 (3H, s).

Compound 3 :

This was prepared by following the similar procedure as for the compound 2, yield : 35%, m.p. 56 °C; 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$; 300 MHz) : 7.81(1H, d, J 8.52 Hz), 7.46 (1H, d, J 8.7 Hz), 6.98 (1H, d, J 8.58 Hz), 6.89 (2H, d, J 8.61 Hz), 6.61 (1H, d, J 16.2 Hz), 2.39 (3H, s).

¹H NMR of indicator 1 (in CDCl₃)

Mass (HRMS) of indicator 1

¹H NMR of indicator 2 (in CDCl₃)

Mass (HRMS) of indicator 2

¹H NMR of indicator 3 (in CDCl₃)

Mass (HRMS) of indicator 3

General procedure for UV-Vis titration :

Solutions of NaOH, KOH and K₂CO₃ were made in 1 : 1 ethanol-H₂O and the solution of indicator **1** was also made in 1 : 1 ethanol-H₂O. But in case of guanidine, solutions of both indicator **1** and guanidine were made in dry ethanol. For guanidine solutions in other organic solvents, both the indicator **1** and guanidine solutions were prepared in UV grade CH₃CN, DMSO, dry CH₃OH and *t*-butanol respectively. Guanidine was liberated from guanidine hydrochloride by sodium ethoxide in ethanol followed by drying under reduced pressure and dissolved in the particular solvent. The concentration of indicator **1** in all the above organic solvents was the same (0.000075 mmol/ml) and the concentration of guanidine was 0.00209 mmol/ml (same in all the above four solvents). The concentrations (mmol/ml) of indicator **1**, NaOH, KOH, K₂CO₃ and guanidine (ethanol) were *ca.* 10⁻³ M.

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